

Deliverable D4.1

Organisation of PWG - Membership, procedures for operation

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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable outlines the terms of reference (ToR) for the Policy Working Group (PWG) established in work package (WP) 4 of ENVRI-FAIR. It describes the overall structure, governance, and operation of this body which brings together relevant experts from the participating research infrastructures (RIs) with the objective of reaching a consensus on a homogeneous set of common FAIR data and service policies for the ENVRI cluster of environmental research RIs.

DELIVERY SLIP

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DELIVERY LOG

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DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the authors (Add the names and email addresses of main authors)

TERMINOLOGY

A master list of the terminology is here:

<https://confluence.egi.eu/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=14452608>

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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Introduction

A key objective for work package (WP) 4 is the creation of a library of common FAIR data and service policies that have a minimum number of special clauses or cases, but have different degrees of granularity that are applicable at the research infrastructure (RI), subdomain and ENVRI community level.

Converging on this homogeneous set of policies requires a clear and consistent interaction between the relevant experts from participating research infrastructures. The Policy Working Group (PWG) has been established to support this dialogue and work towards these harmonized policies.

In the context of WP4 the term “policy” includes those principles necessary for RI service provision, such as access, availability, management, authorship, versioning. However, WP4 does not directly address the technical aspects of these principles but instead works closely with other relevant work packages including WP5 and the domain specific activities in WPs 8-11 to create them. The PWG will also work closely with WP3 for strategic guidance and implementation of the policies recommended by the Policy Working Group.

The governance of the PWG, including the different types of membership, has been defined in the terms of reference (ToR), which are document below.

Terms of Reference

Scope and Purpose

- ENVRI-FAIR Policy Working Group (PWG) will assess the current awareness and level of adoption of the FAIR principles across the different environmental domains represented in the ENVRI cluster of research infrastructures. It will provide recommendations for common policies on the implementation of the FAIR principles at the RI, domain and ENVRI community level.

Composition and Membership

- Meetings of the PWG will be chaired by the leaders of Work Package 4 on an alternating basis.
- A secretary for the PWG will be appointed from the ENVRI-FAIR beneficiary organisations
- A number of permanent members, that are senior staff from selected RIs dealing with policy matters, will represent the different environmental sub-domains committing the necessary time and effort, and using the resources allocated to those partners in the Description of Action for this activity
- Ad hoc members will also be invited to participate at different times to address specific aspects of implementing the FAIR principles at the RI and community level
- Observing members will be invited to participate in the PWG to ensure alignment with other related projects and initiatives including, but not limited to, GO-FAIR, FAIRsFAIR, Enabling FAIR Data.
- The composition of the PWG shall be kept limited to allow efficient work but the PWG shall communicate its work to wide audience in order to get community input and support as stated below in Responsibilities.

Mandate

- The PWG is responsible for delivering Task 4.1 as defined in the ENVRI-FAIR Description of Action (DoA)
- The PWG will report to the ENVRI-FAIR General Assembly
- The PWG will consult with the BEERi, and seek ratification of policy decisions and recommendations with its members

Meetings

The PWG will meet at least twice a year, and as a minimum one of these will be a face – to – face, usually aligned with annual ENVRI-FAIR General Assembly (GA) meetings. Further meetings (both virtual and face-to-face) will be convened as and when deemed necessary by the Chairs of the PWG.

Responsibilities

Chairs of the Policy Working Group are responsible for:

- organising meetings in consultation with the Secretary
- publishing minutes from meetings
- reporting recommendations to BEERi

Members of the Policy Working Group (PWG) are responsible for:

- seeking a consensus among the RIs within their respective sub-domains through active and documented communication
- communicating outcomes of the PWG to the participating domain research infrastructures (RIs)
- recommending ad hoc and observing members for the PWG

Conclusions

The Policy Working Group (PWG) will operate within the Terms of Reference documented above. If there is any need for variance of this governance model it will be the ToR will be modified accordingly with the agreement of the membership and the approval of the ENVRI-FAIR General Assembly (GA).